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Technology Education and Management

Intention to Use AI Tools for Quality Education: A Study of Final Year Undergraduates of University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Quality education can be identified as one of the sustainable development goals and it's needed to develop education at both local and international levels. Technology emerges as a facilitating factor in education and that fosters the pursuit of education among students. As time passed, technology brought a new education tool called artificial intelligent academic tools (AIAT). Further as of today, AI tools have become a prominent factor in enhancing quality education by embracing all of the processes in the education system. The study aims to identify the intention of undergraduate students on the use of AIAT in enhancing quality education. The objective of the study is to identify the significant differences in undergraduate students' intention to use AIAT in quality education based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) Model: perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, voluntariness, and social influence are independent variable while quality education becomes a dependent variable in this study. However, there is a gap in finding empirical evidence on factors affecting the use of AIAT for academic performance in Sri Lanka. The study sample is comprised of 200 final year undergraduate students from five Departments in the Faculty of Commerce and Management Studies, University of Kelaniya by using a simple random sampling technique, and it represents a diverse range of respondents based on their age, gender, working experiences, educational qualifications, primary data are gathered through an online questionnaire and analyzed using IBM SPSS statistics software. An overall analysis is performed based on descriptive statistics, regression analysis, correlation analysis, and ANOVA t-test. The study objectives indicate that all four factors have a significant positive relationship with the quality of education and that AIAT is helpful in filling students' academic performance gap when engaging in academic assignments and projects. Furthermore, this study provides significant contributions to the university system by encouraging university students and lecturers to be active parties in quality education by improving their awareness and interest in the AIAT and blending it's in the education processes.

Keywords: artificial intelligent, academic tools, quality education, undergraduates